

Machine Learning Based Trust Aggregation for IoT Systems

Pasindu Manisha Kuruppuarachchi*, Alan McGibney†, Susan Rea‡ and Bernd-Ludwig Wenning §

Nimbus Research Centre, Munster Technological University

Cork, Ireland

Email: *pasindu.kuruppuarachchi@mtu.ie, †alan.mcgibney@mtu.ie, ‡susan.rea@mtu.ie, §berndludwig.wenning@mtu.ie

Abstract—IoT systems consist of multiple heterogeneous sensors, actuators, and control logic. These systems not only collect data from the physical world around us, they play a critical role in supporting decision-making processes. Trust is essential in this context, as decision-makers must rely on the system's ability to perform its assigned tasks reliably. To ensure system-level trust, a trust analyser is implemented to assess the trustworthiness of IoT systems across seven distinct evaluation categories. Various tools and techniques can be applied within these categories, and the accuracy of each tool must be considered when aggregating trust evaluations to produce a representative trust score. To address this, several machine learning based aggregation methods are explored and compared, including Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and the Tsetlin Machine (TM). ANN and TM achieved 98% accuracy in correctly detecting trust attacks, while ANFIS achieved 76% accuracy. In addition, both ANFIS and TM offer interpretability, providing valuable insight into how they detect and flag attacks within the IoT system.

Index Terms—Trust, IoT Systems, Cybersecurity, Tsetlin Machine, Fuzzy Logic, Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid proliferation of the Internet of Things (IoT) has led to the widespread deployment of interconnected devices across various domains, including smart homes, healthcare, industrial automation, and transportation [5]. IoT devices are continuously connected as well as processing and transmitting data across the internet. The scale of deployment creates an increased attack surface and is vulnerable to bad actors. The characteristics of IoT devices (e.g. resource constraints, low power, small form factor) means they generally suffer from privacy, authentication, management and information storage issues [3], all of which can hinder trust in their use.

Real-world incidents highlight the need for an effective trust analysis framework. For example, the 2016 Mirai botnet attack exploited vulnerable IoT devices to launch large-scale Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks, disrupting major online services [10]. Similarly, privacy concerns have emerged with IoT-based smart home assistants, where unauthorised access to personal data has led to breaches [13].

As such, holistic trust management in IoT systems is crucial to ensure the integrity, reliability, and security of data exchanged between devices and users. Traditional security mechanisms, such as encryption and authentication, are necessary

but not sufficient to establish trust, particularly in dynamic and heterogeneous IoT environments. Because some IoT devices are limited in resources such as computational power, memory, and energy, traditional security measures cannot be applied therefore it is essential to design lightweight and efficient trust evaluation methods that can operate effectively under these constraints [19].

This paper extends the Trust Analyser (TA) proposed in [18] for assessing the trustworthiness of IoT systems within a collaborative ecosystem. By deploying multiple tools to evaluate different aspects of an IoT system the evaluation of trust can be improved. However, aggregating the outputs of these tools into a single trust score presents a significant challenge, particularly due to variations in the accuracy of each tool. To address this, the paper explores various trust aggregation methods, with a particular focus on the interpretability of these methods to provide insights into how the overall trust score is derived.

II. BACKGROUND

The Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) defines trust in a system as belief or confidence that the system works as expected, characterised by safety, security, privacy, reliability, and resilience [15]. This belief or confidence can change over time based on the behaviour of the device [20]. There are primarily two approaches to achieving trust in a system: trust by design and trust by evaluation. The *trust by design* approach involves implementing systems using a trust-based architecture to ensure that all components adhere to trusted implementation principles such as secure coding practices, data integrity verifications and robust authentication [17]. The *trust by evaluation* approach builds confidence in systems, individuals, or processes by assessing their behaviour and performance through data analysis. It offers an objective, evidence-based way to judge trustworthiness, especially in dynamic or uncertain settings [23].

Effective trust management in modern IoT systems require both trust by design and trust by evaluation. The proposed TA uses Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to ensure accountability and non-repudiation (trust by design), while continuously assessing system behaviour with trust evaluation tools to detect subtle changes (trust by evaluations). When using multiple trust evaluation tools, their outputs must be

aggregated carefully, accounting for individual inaccuracies. Therefore, trust aggregation is a key consideration.

Trust aggregation in IoT systems is essential for deriving a final trust value by combining multiple trust attributes and metrics. Various aggregation methods have been proposed to accommodate the complexity and dynamic nature of IoT environments. Common techniques include fuzzy logic, Bayesian inference, belief theory, and machine learning. Fuzzy logic handles uncertainty well and is efficient for real-time environments, whereas Bayesian methods offer statistical rigour but are limited by prior dependencies such as initial beliefs or assumptions. Belief theory excels at integrating uncertain and incomplete data, although it requires complex computation. Machine learning approaches are gaining popularity due to their adaptability and predictive power, but they often demand more resources, making them less suitable for resource-constrained IoT devices. Lightweight methods like weighted sum remain widely adopted due to their simplicity and low overhead, despite being less adaptable to complex environments [6].

Another key aspect is the interpretability of aggregation methods, as understanding their outputs is crucial for trust-based decision making. In terms of interpretability, fuzzy logic stands out as the most transparent approach due to its use of human-readable rules, making it easy to explain trust decisions. Bayesian methods offer moderate interpretability by providing a clear probabilistic reasoning process, though understanding priors and posterior updates can be challenging for non-experts. Belief theory, while effective in managing uncertainty and conflicting information, tends to be less intuitive due to its complex evidence combination rules. In contrast, machine learning techniques generally have low interpretability, as their decision-making processes are often opaque, especially in the case of deep learning or ensemble models, making it difficult to trace how specific inputs influence trust scores.

Considering these aspects, the TA should include a trust aggregation method that handles tool inaccuracies effectively and provides interpretable outputs for informed decision-making about the IoT system which is this paper primary contribution. The next section will present the TA trust model, followed by an explanation of trust aggregation, and a detailed discussion of three different trust aggregation methods and their interpretability.

III. TRUST MODEL

Based on the IIC trust characteristics [15], TA adopts these characteristics as Trust Evaluation Categories (TECs). Additionally, to account for system operational conditions, two more TECs; (i) goal analysis and (ii) uncertainty and dependability are introduced.

A. Trust Evaluation Categories

The TECs are classified into two types: active and passive. Safety and privacy are considered passive TECs, while the re-

maining five are actively evaluated through continuous system monitoring.

Safety and privacy are critical to the implementation and management of IoT systems. However, they are difficult to evaluate actively and continuously. Therefore, periodic assessments of these TECs are essential to ensure the system maintains expected levels of trust and performance by getting necessary certification and following standards.

This section discusses the importance of these TECs in IoT systems and explores potential evaluation approaches. Previous work [18] has also identified possible tools such as network security analysers, device anomaly detection tools, etc. that can be implemented for actively monitoring these TECs.

1) *Safety*: Ensuring the safety of IoT systems is crucial, particularly in sectors such as healthcare, transportation, and industrial automation. Failures in IoT-enabled medical devices or autonomous vehicles can have severe consequences. Safety risks in IoT arise from system malfunctions, software vulnerabilities, and external threats that could compromise device functionality [3]. As IoT ecosystems grow more complex, the potential for unexpected interactions between devices increases, making robust testing and validation mechanisms essential.

According to the EU Cyber Resilience Act¹, manufacturers must adhere to rigorous testing and certification processes. Implementing fail-safe mechanisms and redundancy in safety-critical systems can help prevent catastrophic failures [7].

2) *Privacy*: Privacy concerns in IoT arise due to the extensive data collection performed by smart devices. Many IoT applications rely on continuous data gathering, often without explicit user awareness or consent. Sensitive data such as location, health metrics, and personal habits are stored and transmitted, making them vulnerable to unauthorised access or misuse [24]. The lack of user control over data collection and sharing is a significant challenge, particularly in consumer IoT applications [9].

Several regulatory frameworks and standards have been introduced to address IoT privacy risks. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) enforces strict privacy controls, requiring transparency in data collection and processing. The ISO/IEC 29100 privacy framework provides guidelines for ensuring data protection in IoT environments. In addition, privacy-enhancing technologies such as differential privacy, anonymisation techniques, and secure multiparty computation help mitigate data exposure risks [12].

Privacy protection strategies should include strong data encryption, access control mechanisms, and user-centric privacy policies. Moreover, users should be given greater control over their data, including the ability to modify privacy settings and opt out of unnecessary data collection. [21]

3) *Security*: Security is a fundamental aspect of trust in IoT systems. Key security challenges include authentication, encryption, and intrusion detection. However, IoT security

¹<https://www.cyberresilienceact.eu/the-cyber-resilience-act/>

extends beyond these to encompass multiple aspects, including device, user, and environmental security [8].

For device security, it is essential to assess device software-level vulnerabilities by using platforms such as the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) database. Furthermore, implementing a robust access control and monitoring system at both the device and user level is crucial to prevent unauthorised access and potential disruptions.

In an IoT system, additional services can be deployed to make interoperability and deployment easier for example Application Programming Interfaces (API), making API security a critical concern. API endpoints can be exploited in various ways to launch remote attacks on internal systems, posing a significant risk of data breaches and eroding stakeholder trust [4]. Therefore, continuously evaluating the security of all exposed API endpoints is vital to identifying and mitigating potential risks.

4) *Reliability*: Reliability is typically evaluated using metrics such as Quality of Service (QoS). QoS can be defined in various ways, with one of the most common approaches leveraging network quality parameters such as request-response time, throughput, and failure rates. Network parameters are a primary consideration for QoS as network communications form the foundation of integrated IoT systems.

Another key metric for evaluating reliability is Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) [22]. This metric measures the time between consecutive system or communication failures, and the average value is calculated over a period of time. In a reliable IoT system, a higher MTBF indicates that failures are infrequent, reflecting better system stability.

5) *Resilience*: There are two primary metrics used to evaluate resilience under the TEC framework: Recovery Time Objective (RTO) and Recovery Point Objective (RPO) [1].

Ideally, service disruptions should be imperceptible to the requester. RTO measures the time required for a disrupted service to recover and resume normal operations. Simultaneously, RPO calculates the number of requests or data lost during the disruption. In RPO evaluation, the proportion of lost requests or data is assessed to determine the system's ability to minimize impact and maintain continuity.

6) *Goal Analysis*: Goal analysis in IoT systems is a process that helps system owners define, track, and optimise the performance of their applications [5]. Depending on the specific IoT application, goals may vary significantly based on operational needs and business objectives. For instance, one common goal is to enhance connectivity by continuously monitoring network conditions and ensuring that the system maintains specified operational standards. These goals are often subjective and can differ from one deployment to another. To effectively measure success, system owners can establish Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that align with their desired outcomes. These KPIs provide a structured approach to evaluating system performance, identifying inefficiencies, and making data-informed improvements.

7) *Uncertainty and Dependability*: Data certainty, or the level of confidence in the accuracy and reliability of data, is an important criteria in many data driven applications. Analysing data fluctuations in IoT systems helps assess the level of uncertainty and overall dependability. It is vital that IoT systems accurately represent real environmental conditions however noise in the data can often occur, hence establishing and maintaining confidence in the data generated is needed. This can be measured using various methods such as confidence intervals, standard deviation, and interquartile range.

Since an IoT system consists of multiple devices, it is necessary to analyse uncertainty at the individual device level. Identifying faulty or unreliable devices allows system owners to replace them as needed. Additionally, risk calculations can be performed based on the system's dependency on other devices. Network graphs can be utilised to assess dependencies and evaluate the potential cascade effect of data uncertainty and identify potentially vulnerable devices.

IV. TRUST AGGREGATION

There are multiple tools that can be used to capture metrics to measure each TEC [18] and consider a specific trust evaluation duration. As presented in Fig. 1, the TA will collect all the inputs from these tools. Once the TA collects all its inputs, trust analysis is carried out based on TA configurations to determine the IoT system trust score. The following configurations are required for the TA:

- **Trust Analysis Cycle Duration**: Each trust analysis cycle collects all inputs from evaluation tools for a specified duration before calculating the trust score. This evaluation cycle duration is based on the IoT system requirements and it is customisable. As shown in Fig. 1, during an analysis cycle, the TA receives n inputs ($In_{(n)}$) from various evaluation tools, which are then grouped into their corresponding TECs before calculating the trust score.
- **TEC Weights**: Based on use case requirements, system operators can assign weights to specific TECs according to their importance for system trust evaluation. These weights are then used as part of the trust score calculations to prioritise certain characteristics of trust.

These configurations allow system operators to customise the TA to meet their scenario specific requirements. In the current implementation, the TA uses a weighted average method to calculate the final trust score. However, given the multiple inputs from various tools, it is essential to account for the anomaly detection accuracies of individual tools. This prevents the trust score from fluctuating solely on the basis of TEC weights, even if a tool falsely reports issues.

To address this, the TA first aims to determine the possibility of a trust attack by analysing all inputs received during its trust evaluation cycle.

Fig. 1. Trust analysis workflow

APR

A. Trust Attack Detection

To identify the likelihood of a trust attack, the following methods were explored and integrated into the TA due to their high classification accuracy and interpretability:

- Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS):** ANFIS combines the interpretability of fuzzy logic with the learning capabilities of neural networks [16], making it highly effective for modeling complex, non-linear systems such as trust attack detection. It handles uncertainty and imprecision in data through fuzzy rules, while its neural network component adapts and optimises parameters to improve accuracy. Unlike traditional fuzzy systems, which require manual rule definition, ANFIS automatically optimises parameters using gradient-based learning, enhancing both accuracy and generalisation with minimum involvement with expert knowledge. This hybrid approach enables ANFIS to identify subtle patterns indicative of trust attacks, such as malicious behaviour or anomalies in system interactions.
- Neural Networks (NN):** Neural Networks are computational models inspired by the human brain, capable of learning complex patterns from data. In trust attack detection, NNs excel in identifying intricate relationships and anomalies in large datasets [14]. Their layered architecture allows them to extract hierarchical features, making them effective for detecting sophisticated attacks, such as adversarial manipulations or insider threats. However, their "black-box" nature can limit interpretability, which is a critical factor in trust evaluation. Despite this, NNs remain a powerful tool for detecting trust attacks due to their adaptability and high accuracy.
- Tsetlin Machine (TM):** The Tsetlin Machine is a novel machine learning model based on propositional logic and the Tsetlin Automaton. Unlike traditional neural networks, TMs use logical expressions to represent data patterns, offering high interpretability and transparency [11]. This makes them particularly suitable for the detection of trust attacks, where understanding the decision-making process is crucial. TMs are computationally efficient and robust to noise, enabling them to detect trust attacks, such as data poisoning or adversarial inputs, with high precision. Their ability to provide human-readable rules makes them

an attractive choice for applications requiring explainable AI in trust evaluation.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Application Scenario & Experiment Setup

The push toward personalised manufacturing is transforming the traditional, centralised, mass-production model into a more decentralised, flexible, and customer-centric approach. Large-scale manufacturing units struggle with short product life cycles and market fluctuations, making modular plants a cost-effective and adaptable alternative. Ensuring the trustworthiness of these plants is crucial, particularly for manufacturing critical system components. The TA can assign trust scores to these modularised manufacturing plants, support work distribution decisions, and help prioritise the resolution of trust related issues.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, once tools submit their findings to the TA, it attempts to detect trust attacks, preventing unnecessary trust score fluctuations caused by individual tool false positive inputs. If the TA detects a trust attack, it calculates the confidence level of the attack along with TEC weights to update the trust score. Otherwise, the trust score remains unchanged.

To assess the effectiveness and challenges of various trust aggregation and attack detection methods, an initial test was conducted using a synthetic dataset designed to reflect real-world applications.

This dataset simulates the output of TEC tools capturing network and device anomalies in a modularised manufacturing environment, incorporating two key features: a Boolean flag (0 or 1) indicating the presence of an anomaly and a continuous value (ranging from 1 to 20) representing either the degree of deviation from normal operation or the tool's confidence in detecting the anomaly. Additionally, a third data point identifies trust attacks where a value of 1 is assigned if the Boolean flag is 1 and the continuous value exceeds 10; otherwise, it remains 0. This structured approach mirrors real-world conditions, where outputs from multiple tools may contribute to detection of trust attacks. The goal of this experiment is to identify which method can present trust attack logic in a simple, understandable way while maintaining high accuracy.

To challenge trust attack detection methods, noise was introduced by flipping 20% of the 1,000 dataset rows. Initially, 266

Fig. 2. ANFIS membership functions and fuzzy rules

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----- Clause 1 is always 0 -----
['Clause output is always 0',
 'Input 1 <= 0.0 AND 1.0 < Input 2',
 '0.0 < Input 1 AND 12.0 < Input 2',
 'Input 2 <= 10.0']

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Fig. 3. Tsetlin machine rules for attack classification (input 1 = presence of an attack (0 or 1), input 2 = deviation from original value range or confidence of anomaly detection (1 to 20))

rows indicated an attack; after adding noise, this increased to 276.

For training, 80% of the data (800 rows) was used, with 213 representing an attack. The remaining 200 rows were used for testing, where 69 rows indicated an attack.

TABLE I
AGGREGATION METHODS EVALUATION

Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
ANFIS	0.90	0.76	1
ANN	0.97	0.98	0.92
TM	0.97	0.98	0.92

B. ANFIS

As shown in Table I, the ANFIS method achieves an overall accuracy of 0.9 while maintaining a perfect recall value. This indicates that the model correctly identified all actual positive cases. However, with a precision of 0.76, not all positive predictions were correct.

Fig. 2 presents the learned membership functions, fuzzy rules, and the final output formula with its corresponding weights. This visualisation helps TA users understand which value ranges are considered when determining the membership function for each input and which rule is activated. Based on the selected fuzzy rule formula, the output is then calculated.

Finally, if the output value exceeds 0.5, the instance is classified as 1 (attack); otherwise, it is classified as 0 (not an attack).

C. ANNs

ANNs excel in classification tasks due to their ability to capture complex, non-linear relationships within data. As shown in Table I, ANN achieved an accuracy of 0.97 while maintaining higher precision than ANFIS. The recall difference between ANFIS and ANN is 0.08.

However, interpreting ANN outputs remains a challenge, and further experiments with larger datasets may influence accuracy. The lack of interpretability is a critical concern, particularly in trust analysis, where understanding the specific factors that trigger correct trust attack detection is essential.

D. Tsetlin Machine

The Tsetlin Machine (TM) achieved an accuracy of 0.97 on the provided dataset while maintaining similar precision and recall values to ANNs. The key advantage of TM is its ability to generate interpretable results.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, four clauses were used for attack classification. Clauses 1 and 3 support classifying inputs as an attack (odd clause numbers = class 1), while clauses 2 and 4 oppose it (even clause numbers = class 0). This clause classification is how TM is implemented.

Based on TM's learned clauses, clause 1 is always 0, and clause 3 is the only one voting for an attack (class 1). However, in TM's implementation, if the votes for both classes are equal, the model defaults to classifying the output as class 1 (attack).

Considering the synthetic data's trust attack logic, clause 3 aligns most closely with it, stating that input 1 must be greater than 0 and input 2 must be greater than 12. This closely resembles the original logic, where a trust attack is flagged whenever input 1 equals 1 and input 2 exceeds 10.

Based on initial results, TM has demonstrated favourable outcomes in detecting attacks and providing more interpretable

output than ANFIS. This allows system operators to easily understand the reasons behind trust score fluctuations.

As presented in Fig. 1, the TA first determines whether any attacks are present in the system. It then calculates a trust score, taking into account the weights of the TECs and the confidence level of the attack classification. Currently, the trust score is computed using a weighted sum based on the TEC weights multiply by the confidence level and scaled to a value between 0 and 100.

The confidence level represents how certain the attack detection method is in its classification of an attack. In ANFIS, this corresponds to the activation value of the fuzzy rules. However, in TM, it is derived by passing the difference between Class 1 and Class 0 votes through a sigmoid function [2]. In the current trust score calculation, incorporating the confidence level helps control the rate at which the trust score increases or decreases. If the TA is highly confident that a trust attack is present, the trust score can be significantly reduced. Conversely, if the TA is highly confident that no attack is present, the trust score can be increased accordingly.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Trust is a critical factor in decision-making, especially in mission-critical systems where confidence in the process is essential. To support informed decisions, the proposed TA evaluates IoT systems across seven TECs. Since TEC findings may contain inaccuracies, the TA must account for these when aggregating results. To address this, the TA predicts the likelihood of a real trust attack in the system and uses this confidence level to calculate a trust score.

For attack prediction, ANFIS, NN, and the TM were evaluated. On a synthetic dataset, TM and NN achieved the highest accuracy; however, only TM maintained strong interpretability by providing an easily understandable classification logic. This is an important factor for decision-makers who need to understand why trust attacks are detected. Future work will focus on expanding this approach with real-world operational data and developing a complete TA execution pipeline for enhanced reliability and robustness.

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